

COMBINING ABILITY ANALYSIS STUDIES FOR SEED COTTON YIELD AND COMPONENT TRAITS IN *DESI*COTTON (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)

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Abstract

The present investigation entitled "Study on heterosis and combining ability for yield, its components and fibre characters in desi cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)" was undertaken to estimate general combining ability (GCA) of the parents and specific combining ability effects (SCA) of the crosses. The experimental material comprised of 30 F₁ hybrids obtained by crossing 6 lines with 5 testers in line x tester mating system. The analysis of variance for combining ability revealed significant general combining ability effects (GCA) and specific combining ability effects (SCA) for all the traits. The male parent JLA 505 was found good general combiner for four characters viz., Upper half mean length (mm), Fibre fineness (Micronaire) ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$), Fibre strength (g/tex) and Uniformity ratio (%) with significant general combining ability effects (GCA). The female PA 809 was found as the good general combiner for four characters viz., days to 50 percent flowering, plant height (cm), boll weight (g) and days to maturity. The female PA 785 was the good general combiner for number of bolls per plant, while male JLA 505 was the good general combiner for boll weight and plant height (cm). PA 402 found good general combiner for number of bolls per plant and seed cotton yield per plant. There was close association between per se performance and general combining ability effects as well as specific combining ability effects for most of the characters. Observations on various characters indicated that the crosses showing high heterosis with high SCA effects had high per se performance and they entangled at least one parent with good general combining ability effects (GCA). The cross combinations PA 785 x PA 810, PA 873 x AKA 8, PA 833 x PA 08 and PA 809 x AKA 8 exhibited significant and desirable specific combining ability effects for most of the yield and fibre quality traits.

Key words : General combining ability, Specific combining ability, Seed cotton yield

Introduction

Cotton, the king of fibres, occupies a pre-eminent position as a commercial crop in India. Cotton also known as 'white gold' as it is preferred by farmers as cash crop beside other field crops. It is grown commercially in the temperate and tropical regions of more than 70 countries. India is perhaps the first country to make use of cotton. Cotton, the 'white gold' enjoys a pre-eminent status among all cash crops in the country. It is grown commercially in the temperate and tropical regions of more than 70 countries. Specific areas of production include countries such as China, USA, India, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Turkey, Australia, Greece, Brazil, Egypt etc. Genetic improvement in *desi* cotton could be gained either through selection or exploitation of specific hybrid. Therefore, more emphasis should be given to increase the seed cotton yield per unit area by developing hybrids with short stature, big boll size, longer staple length with sustained yield in multiple environments. To achieve such desirable characteristics in a new cultivar, proper breeding strategies should be followed. There is an urgent need to promote those cottons that could come closer in quality to the most sought by modern textile mills. For development of superior and heterotic hybrids in cotton, it is essential to utilize large number of available germplasm. In the context of quality assessment, high volume instrument testing is universally accepted by the industry and is becoming a requirement, enabling cotton to be marketed more directly on textile mill needs rather than the traditional grade, staple and micronaire. This has contributed to the development and acceptance of high quality hybrids and varieties. Line x tester analysis provides a systematic approach for selection of appropriate parents on the basis of general combining ability effects (GCA) and superior crosses on the basis of specific combining ability effects (SCA). Combining ability describes the breeding value of parental lines to produce hybrids. Sprague and Tatum (1942) used the terms general combining ability (GCA) to designate the average performance of a line in hybrid combinations and specific combining ability (SCA) as deviation in performance of a cross combination from that predicted on the basis of the general combining abilities of the parents involved in the cross. In order to choose appropriate parents for hybridization as well as specific crosses, it is essential to determine the combining ability of

parents and specific combining ability (SCA) of cross combinations by using line x tester analysis. The method has been widely used by plant breeders. This method was applied to improve self and cross-pollinated crop plants.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was undertaken to Study of combining for seed cotton yield, yield contributing and fibre quality traits in Desi Cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). Twenty four hybrid combinations derived by crossing 6 *arboreum* lines with 5 testers and their ten parents along with 2 checks were tested at Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh farm, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani during *kharif* season of 2023-24. The mean values of all the treatments for the characters under study were worked out. Standard error and critical difference at 1 and 5 per cent level of significance were calculated by using the formula (Panse and Sukhatme, 1961). The general combining ability effects of lines and testers, whereas specific combining ability effects of cross combinations were worked out. The test of significance of different genotypes was done according to the procedure given by Kempthorne (1957). The nature of gene action involved in the expression of various quantitative traits is also revealed.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the crosses showing high heterosis and high per se performance involved the parents possessing either high x high, high x low and low x low general combining ability effects of parents indicating importance of non additive genetic variance. The combining ability analysis gives useful information regarding selection of parents based on performance of their hybrids. While specific combining ability helps in selection of specific cross combination.

General combining ability effects (GCA)

The data regarding general combining ability effects is presented in Table No.1. In the present investigations, the female parents PA 785 (-1.45) and PA 809 (-2.05) expressed significant negative general combining ability effect (GCA) for days to 50 % flowering. The male parents CNA 1032 (-1.75) and JLA 505 (-1.350) expressed negative desirable general combining ability effect (GCA) for days to 50% flowering. Hence these parents are found good general combiners for days to 50 percent

flowering. Similar findings were observed by Azhar *et al.* (2007), Kalpande *et al.* (2008) and Deshmukh *et al.* (2021).

Amongst the testers, JLA 505 (-1.70), PA 402 (-0.70) and exhibited highly significant negative general combining ability (GCA) effects for seed cotton yield per plant. Whereas, among lines PA 809 (-2.90) and CNA 1032 (-2.40), PA 785 (-1.00) recorded negative significant general combining ability effects (GCA) for days to maturity. Hence these parents are found good general combiner for days to maturity. Similar findings were observed by Dai Gang *et al.* (2012) and Ranganath *et al.* (2013).

The female parents PA 873 (2.55), PA 809 (3.65) and PA 809 (4.45) recorded highly significant positive general combining ability effects (GCA), while in case of male parents JLA 505 (4.21), PA 402 (3.88) and PA 402 (3.88) exhibited positive significant general combining effects (GCA), followed by PA 810 (2.80) for plant height. Hence these parents are found good general combiners plant height. Similar findings were observed by Patel and Chaudhary *et al.* (2015), Pundir *et al.* (2016) and Deshmukh *et al.* (2021).

Amongst the female, none of the female parent has exhibited significant positive general combining ability effects (GCA) for number of sympodia per plant. In case of male parents, JLA 505 (2.26) recorded significantly positive general combining ability effects (GCA) for number of sympodia per plant. Hence, JLA 505 is found good general combiner for number of sympodia per plant. Similar findings were reported by Deshmukh *et al.* (2021) and Mudhalvan *et al.* (2021).

Amongst the female parents, PA 785 (1.71) and PA 809 (1.01) exhibited significant positive general combining ability effects (GCA) for number of bolls per plant. In case of male parents, PA 402 (1.01) and JLA 505 (0.85) recorded significant positive general combining ability effects (GCA) for number of bolls per plant. Hence these parents are found good general combiner for number bolls per plant. The results are in agreement with the results of Vekariya *et al.* (2017), Deshmukh *et al.* (2021) and Mudhalvan *et al.* (2021).

Amongst female parents, lines PA 809 (0.18), PA 904 (0.11), PA 785 (0.09) and CNA 1032 (0.07) showed positive significant general combining ability effect (GCA) for boll weight, while in case of testers JLA 505 (0.17) and showed positive significant general combining ability effects (GCA) for boll weight. Hence these parents are found good general combiner for number boll weight. Similar findings were observed by Patel and Chaudhary *et al.* (2015) and Premalatha *et al.* (2020).

Among the parents, none of the parent has displayed positive general combining ability effect (GCA) for ginning outturn. The female parents PA 873 (-1.14) recorded significant negative general combining ability effect (GCA) for ginning outturn. The results are in agreement with the reports of Chaudhary *et al.* (2015), Deshmukh *et al.* (2021) and Mudhalvan *et al.* (2021).

Amongst females PA 809 (0.66), PA 785 (0.42) and CNA 1032 (0.32) has recorded positive significant general combining ability effect (GCA) for upper half mean length. The male parents JLA 505 (0.62) and PA 08 (0.33) has exhibited positive significant general combining ability effects (GCA) for upper half mean length. Hence, these parents are found good general combiners for upper half mean length. Similar findings were observed by Saravanan *et al.* (2010) and Shinde *et al.* (2022).

Among the female parents PA 785 (-0.66) and PA 809 (-0.10) has recorded negative significant general combining ability for fibre fineness. The male parents PA 402 (-0.06) and JLA 505 (-0.06) has exhibited negative significant general combining ability for fibre fineness. Hence, these parents are found good general combiners for fibre fineness. Similar findings were observed by Shakeel *et al.* (2016) and Shinde *et al.* (2022).

Among the female parent, PA 904 (1.03), PA 785 (1.22) and PA 809 (0.37) has exhibited significant positive general combining ability effect (GCA) for fibre strength. The male parents, PA 08 (0.47) and JLA 505 (1.00) recorded positive significant general combining ability effects

(GCA). Hence, these parents are found good general combiners for fibre strength. Similar findings were observed by Deosarkar *et al.* (2014), Lokesh *et al.* (2018) and Shinde *et al.* (2022). Among the female parent, PA 904 (2.08) and PA 809 (1.48) has displayed positive general combining ability effect (GCA) for uniformity ratio. The male parent JLA 505 (2.36) recorded positive significant general combining ability effects (GCA) for uniformity ratio. Hence, these parents are found good found general combiners for uniformity ratio. Similar results were reported Thiyagu *et al.* (2019) and Shinde *et al.* (2022) for these characters.

Amongst the six females, PA 785 (2.71), PA 904 (1.33) and PA 809 (2.13) exhibited highly significant positive general combining ability (GCA) effects for seed cotton yield per plant. The male parents PA 402 (2.57) and JLA 505 (1.43) recorded significantly positive general combining ability effect (GCA). Hence these parents are found good general combiner for seed cotton yield per plant. Similar results were quoted by Vekariya *et al.* (2017), Shinde *et al.* (2018), Nand *et al.* (2019) and Mudhalvan *et al.* (2021).

Specific combining ability effects (SCA)

The data regarding specific combining ability effects is presented in Table No.2. Amongst the crosses, eight crosses have recorded significant negative specific combining ability effects (SCA) for days to 50 per cent flowering. The hybrid PA 833 x PA 402 (-6.63) exhibited highest negative significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) for days to 50 per cent flowering followed by the crosses PA 785 x PA 810 (-5.38) and PA 904 x PA 402 (-3.83). The results are in agreements with the reports of Azhar *et al.* (2007) and lokesh *et al.* (2018) for days to 50% flowering.

Twelve crosses recorded significant negative specific combining ability effects (SCA) for days to maturity. The hybrid PA 833 x PA 402 (-6.10) displayed highest negative significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) for days to maturity followed by CNA 1032 x AKA 8 (-6.01), PA 785 x PA 810 (-5.83) and PA 809 x AKA 8 (-4.51). The results are in agreements with the reports of Dhamayanthi (2011) and Deosarkar *et al.* (2014).

Eleven crosses recorded significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for plant height. The hybrid PA 809 x AKA 8 (18.46) showed highest positive significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) for plant height followed by CNA 1032 x PA 402 (11.51) and PA 833 x PA 402 (10.21). The results are in agreements with the reports of Sakhare *et al.* (2005) and Lokesh *et al.* (2018).

Amongst crosses, seven crosses exhibited significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for number of sympodia per plant. The hybrid PA 809 x AKA 8 (5.48) showed highest positive significant specific combining ability effect (SCA) for number of sympodia per plant followed by PA 873 x JLA 505 (4.03) and PA 833 x PA 810 (3.55). The results are in agreements with the reports of Jatoi *et al.* (2011) and Lokesh *et al.* (2018).

Amongst the crosses, eight crosses exhibited significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for number of bolls per plant. The hybrid PA873 x AKA 8 (4.23) had recorded highest positive significant specific combining ability (SCA) followed by PA 833 x PA 08 (3.68) and PA 785 x PA 810 (3.45) for number of bolls per plant. The results are in agreements with the reports of Pundir *et al.* (2016), Lokesh *et al.* (2018) and Premalatha *et al.* (2020).

Amongst the crosses, thirteen were having significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for boll weight. The cross combination PA 873 x AKA 8 (0.73) had recorded highest positive significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) followed by the crosses PA 904 x PA 402 (0.56) and PA 809 x AKA 8 (0.56) for boll weight. The results are in agreements with the reports of Lokesh *et al.* (2018) and Premalatha *et al.* (2020).

Amongst crosses, only four cross combinations have displayed significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for ginning outturn. The hybrid PA 809 x AKA 8 (4.38) recorded highest positive significant

specific combining ability effects (SCA) followed by the crosses CNA 1032 x PA 402 (3.85) and PA 904 x PA 402 (3.61) for ginning outturn. Similar kinds of results were reported by Lokesh *et al.* (2018) and Kanasagra *et al.* (2022).

Amongst the crosses, eleven crosses exhibited significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for upper half mean length. The cross combination PA 873 x AKA 8 (2.71) showed the highest significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for upper half mean length followed by the crosses PA 833 x AKA 8 (2.45) and PA 833 x PA 08 (2.32). The results are in agreements with the reports of Lokesh *et al.* (2018), Premalatha *et al.* (2020) and Kanasagra *et al.* (2022).

Amongst the crosses, eleven crosses exhibited significant negative specific combining ability effects (SCA) for fibre fineness. While the cross-combination PA 904 x PA 810 (-0.75) exhibited significant negative specific combining ability (SCA) for fibre fineness followed by PA 873 x PA 08 (-0.72) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (-0.57). The results are in agreements with the reports of Patil *et al.* (2017) and Lokesh *et al.* (2018).

Amongst the crosses, twelve crosses exhibited significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for fibre strength. The cross combination PA 833 x PA 08 (3.94) showed the highest significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for fibre strength followed by PA 873 x AKA 8 (2.87). The results are in agreements with the reports of Patil *et al.* (2017), Lokesh *et al.* (2018) and Premalatha *et al.* (2020).

Amongst the crosses, thirteen crosses exhibited significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for uniformity ratio. The cross combination PA 873 x AKA 8 (5.53) exhibited highest positive significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) for uniformity ratio followed by the crosses PA 833 x PA 08 (4.81) and PA 809 x AKA 8 (4.43). The results are in agreement with findings of Thiyaagu *et al.* (2019) and Manonmani *et al.* (2020).

Thirteen crosses exhibited highly significant positive specific combining ability effects (SCA) for seed cotton yield per plant. The cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 (10.23) recorded highest positive significant specific combining ability effects (SCA) for seed cotton yield per plant followed by PA 873 x AKA 8 (8.49) and PA 785 x PA 810 (7.86) for seed cotton yield per plant. The crosses having significant positive combining ability effects involved parents with good x good general combining ability effects, good x poor general combining ability effects, average x good general combining ability effects and good x average general combining ability effects (Table No. 3). The results are in agreements with the reports of Pundir *et al.* (2016), Vekariya *et al.* (2017), Shinde *et al.* (2018), Nand *et al.* (2019), Manonmani *et al.* (2020), Premalatha *et al.* (2020) and Chakholoma *et al.* (2022).

Conclusion :

The parental lines PA 785, PA 402, PA 809, PA 904 and JLA 505 were found good general combiners for seed cotton yield per plant and other yield contributing characters. These parents can be used in hybridization programme to develop high seed cotton yielding hybrids.

The hybrids PA 904 x PA 402, PA 833 x PA 08 and PA 785 x PA 810 were found to be best specific cross combinations for fibre quality traits. These hybrids could be tested at multilocations and seasons to release for commercial cultivation.

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Declaration of Conflicts of Interest : The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

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Table 3: Top five hybrids with general combining ability effects (GCA) of the parents

Hybrid	GCA (lines)	GCA (testers)	SCA for crosses	Combiners
PA 904 x PA 402	1.33**	2.57**	10.23**	Good x Good
PA 785 x PA 810	2.71**	-0.03	7.86**	Poor x Good
CNA 1032 x PA 402	0.23	2.57**	6.88**	Average x Good
PA 809 x PA 08	2.13**	0.23	4.08**	Good x Average
PA 809 x JLA 505	2.13**	1.43**	2.73**	Good x Good

Table 1 Estimates of general combining ability effects (GCA) of lines

Parents	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Number of sympodia/ plant	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight	Plant height	Ginning out turn	Upper half mean length	Fibre fineness/ Micronaire	Fibre strength	Uniformity ratio	Seed cotton yield/plant
PA 785	-1.45**	-1.00**	0.15	1.71**	0.09**	3.65**	0.61	0.42**	-0.66**	1.22**	-0.81**	2.71**
PA 873	2.45**	2.20**	-1.45*	-1.48**	-0.10**	2.55*	-1.14*	-0.46**	0.30**	-0.13	-0.11	-0.75**
PA 833	0.05	1.10**	-0.55	-2.18**	-0.36**	-5.55**	-0.24	-1.14**	0.30**	-2.33**	-1.81**	-5.67**
PA 904	2.75**	3.00**	1.05	0.61	0.11**	-2.75*	0.57	0.21	0.00	1.03**	2.08**	1.33**
PA 809	-2.05**	-2.90**	0.35	1.01*	0.18**	4.45**	0.10	0.66**	-0.10**	0.37*	1.48**	2.13**
CNA 1032	-1.75**	-2.40**	0.45	0.31	0.07*	-2.35	0.09	0.32*	0.17**	-0.15	-0.81**	0.23
S.E. (Gi-Gj)	0.35	0.40	0.93	0.52	0.04	1.67	0.72	0.20	0.04	0.25	0.22	0.34
CD @5%	0.71	0.83	1.91	1.07	0.09	3.43	1.48	0.41	0.10	0.51	0.46	0.70
CD @1%	0.97	1.12	2.57	1.44	0.13	4.62	2.00	0.55	0.13	0.69	0.63	0.94

Table 1 Estimates of general combining ability effects (GCA) of testers

Parents	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Number of sympodia/ plant	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight	Plant height	Ginning out turn	Upper half mean length	Fibre fineness/ Micronaire	Fibre strength	Uniformity ratio	Seed cotton yield/plant
PA 810	-0.01	0.13	0.85	2.80*	-0.15	-0.00	-0.20	-0.26	0.08*	-1.04**	0.20	-0.03
PA 08	1.31**	0.55*	-1.98**	-0.03	-0.48	0.04	-0.44	0.33*	0.05	0.47**	-0.21	0.23
AKA 8	-0.18	1.71**	-1.98**	-10.86**	-1.23**	-0.27**	-0.36	-0.74**	-0.00	-0.75**	-2.63**	-4.19**
PA 402	0.23	-0.70*	0.85	3.88**	1.01**	0.05	0.47	0.05	-0.06*	0.30	0.28	2.57**
JLA 505	-1.35**	-1.70**	2.26**	4.21**	0.85*	0.17**	0.55	0.62**	-0.06*	1.00**	2.36**	1.43**
S.E. (Gi-Gj)	0.32	0.37	0.85	1.53	0.47	0.04	0.66	0.18	0.04	0.22	0.20	0.31
CD @5%	0.65	0.76	1.74	3.13	0.97	0.08	1.35	0.37	0.09	0.46	0.42	0.64
CD @1%	0.88	1.02	2.35	4.22	1.31	0.12	1.83	0.50	0.12	0.62	0.57	0.86

* and** indicated significance at 5 and 1 per cent respectively.

Table 3 Estimates of specific combining ability effects (SCA) of the crosses for various characters

Hybrids	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Number of sympodia/ plant	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight	Seed cotton yield/plant	Ginning outturn	Upper half mean length	Fibre fineness/ Micronaire	Fibre strength	Uniformity ratio
PA 785 x PA 810	-5.38**	1.10	2.85	3.45**	0.51**	7.86**	2.51*	2.05**	-0.13	1.50**	4.40**
PA 785 x PA 08	2.28**	-2.56	-2.31	-2.21*	-0.48**	-4.85**	2.13	-0.79*	-0.25*	-1.81**	-3.68**
PA 785 x AKA 8	-3.21**	-4.23	-1.31	-3.46**	-0.45**	-1.12*	-4.55**	-2.21**	-0.19*	-1.49**	-4.76**
PA 785 x PA 402	3.36**	-0.48	0.85	1.78*	0.32**	-2.24**	-1.98	0.48	0.51*	1.15**	1.81**
PA 785 x JLA 505	2.95**	6.18*	-0.06	0.45	0.10	0.35	1.88	0.47	0.06	0.65	2.23**
PA 873 x PA 810	-0.28	7.20*	3.45*	-0.35	-0.42**	-4.16**	0.80	-0.40	0.24*	0.76	-3.80**
PA 873 x PA 08	-2.11**	-0.96	-3.71*	-2.01*	0.26**	-0.48	-0.70	-0.85*	-0.72*	-1.45**	-1.38**
PA 873 x AKA 8	-1.11	6.36*	-5.71**	4.23**	0.73**	8.49**	2.11	2.72**	-0.21*	2.87**	5.53**
PA 873 x PA 402	1.46*	-20.38**	1.95	-0.51	-0.60**	-4.87**	-2.71*	-1.62**	0.34*	-2.38**	-1.88**
PA 873 x JLA 505	2.05**	7.78**	4.03*	-1.35	0.02	1.02	0.49	0.16	0.34*	0.21	1.53**
PA 833 x PA 810	3.11**	-6.70*	3.55*	-0.65	0.24**	3.30**	-1.49	-0.02	0.19*	-1.03*	0.90*
PA 833 x PA 08	0.78	9.13**	3.38*	3.68**	0.47**	6.79**	2.02	2.32**	0.37*	3.94**	4.81**
PA 833 x AKA 8	5.28**	6.96*	3.38*	1.43	0.54**	7.01**	1.61	2.45**	-0.06	2.07**	2.23**

Hybrids	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Number of sympodia/plant	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight	Seed cotton yield/plant	Ginning outturn	Upper half mean length	Fibre fineness/ Micronaire	Fibre strength	Uniformity ratio
PA 833 x PA 402	-6.63**	10.21**	-5.95**	-2.81**	-0.52**	-7.65**	-1.69	-3.14**	-0.40*	-3.28**	-5.68**
PA 833 x JLA 505	-2.55**	-19.61**	-4.36**	-1.65	-0.74**	-9.46**	-0.45	-1.61**	-0.10	-1.68**	-2.26**
PA 904 x PA 810	-0.58	10.00**	-2.05	-0.45	0.04	-0.55	-1.60	0.46	-0.75*	1.99**	0.50
PA 904 x PA 08	0.08	-0.16	-2.21	-1.11	-0.03	-1.67**	-0.13	0.66*	0.22*	-0.22	2.41**
PA 904 x AKA 8	3.58**	-13.83**	1.78	-1.36	-0.67**	-9.95**	-0.84	-3.70**	0.43*	-2.90**	-3.66**
PA 904 x PA 402	-3.83**	3.91	2.95	2.38**	0.56**	10.23**	3.61**	1.94**	-0.50*	1.24**	2.41**
PA 904 x JLA 505	0.75	0.08	-0.46	0.55	0.11	1.98**	-1.03	0.63	0.59*	-0.10	-1.66**
PA 809 x PA 810	-0.78	-20.20**	-7.35**	-3.85**	-0.67**	-10.70**	-1.23	-3.83**	0.35*	-5.44**	-4.40**
PA 809 x PA 08	-0.61	3.13	3.48*	2.48**	0.09	4.08**	-1.02	1.11**	-0.01	1.78**	0.01
PA 809 x AKA 8	-1.11	18.46**	5.48**	2.23*	0.56**	6.25**	4.38**	1.59**	-0.50*	2.66**	4.43**
PA 809 x PA 402	5.96**	-4.78	-2.35	-2.01*	-0.23**	-2.36**	-1.07	1.04**	0.60*	0.85*	0.01
PA 809 x JLA 505	-3.45**	3.38	0.73	1.15	0.24**	2.73**	-1.04	0.08	-0.44*	0.15	-0.06
CNA 1032 x PA 810	3.91**	8.60**	-0.45	1.85*	0.30**	4.24**	1.01	1.75**	0.07	2.23**	2.40**
CNA 1032 x PA 08	-0.41	-8.56**	1.38	-0.81	-0.31**	-3.87**	-2.29	-2.44**	0.40*	-2.23**	-2.18**
CNA 1032 x AKA 8	-3.41**	-13.73**	-3.61*	-3.06**	-0.70**	-10.64**	-2.71*	-0.86*	0.56*	-3.21**	-3.76**
CNA 1032 x PA 402	-0.33	11.51**	2.55	1.18	0.46**	6.88**	3.85**	1.28**	-0.57*	2.43**	3.31**
CNA 1032 x JLA 505	0.25	2.18	0.13	0.85	0.25**	3.38**	0.14	0.27	-0.47*	0.78	0.23
S.E.+	0.55	2.65	1.47	0.82	0.07	0.54	1.15	0.32	0.07	0.39	0.36

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively